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SPACE TALKS

URBAN INFORMALITY: A PERSISTENT MATTER OF CONCERN

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Looking across the theoretical margins, the Chinese concept of *guanxi* – a more extensively studied form of informal social order – offers a helpful comparative lens (see also the back page). Such heuristics are part of a wider landscape of culturally embedded relational epistemologies and practices across the Global South, often overlooked or flattened by stagnant concepts of informality. To recognize the significance of such practices, these theoretically marginalised concepts must be studied in greater contextual depth and compared, despite the difficulty of discerning universal categories.

In this light, what is often dismissed as informal may in fact reflect a deeper heuristic and epistemological blind spot within dominant systems of knowledge and global standardisation. As such, we argue that informality should not be treated as a residual category but rather reclaimed as a *collective matter of concern* – one that demands critical attention, theoretical openness, and a commitment to epistemic plurality.

Twinning practices of intimacy and economy that adapt quickly in response to the volatile uncertainty of life in Myanmar. The logic of *nalehmu* in Yangon's street vending represents long-standing, culturally specific, and historically grown practices of an intimate economy (Wilson, 2004). These practices superimpose, contest, complement and therefore affect the implementation of formal regulations. Yet, they also persist beyond formal and often externally imposed systems of objectification in Myanmar's postcolonial urban landscape.

Call to Concern: Figuring out Informalities

Informality has become a loose and dismissive catch-all term for diverse, non-formal practices and social dynamics unfolding in urban frontiers (Bunwell et al., 2012). Unearthing new heuristics – particularly in postcolonial settings across the Global South, where concepts from the Global North are far too often uncritically transferred – is therefore crucial if we are to aspire to a more pluralistic understanding of space.

From Matters of Fact to Matters of Concern

In academic discourses, the concept of informality is increasingly discarded: Caught up in a static formal-informal dichotomy, it is widely critiqued for its ahistoricity, lack of precision in describing new phenomena, and limitations in diag-

In Myanmar, formal institutionalisation does not necessarily correlate with justice, transparency, efficiency or societal benefit. On the streets of Yangon, vendors and customers alike navigate the intricate web of pricing, territories and services through local and relational networks. Known as *nalehmu* (the notion of understanding in Burmese), this relational logic knits together mutual obligations and trust established through long-term interactions.

This issue of SPACE TALKS critically explores how the neglect of informality as a concept can obscure complex mechanisms of urban life at the theoretical margins in the Global South.

malisation processes emphasised rule of law and transparency but failed to consider Myanmar's relational networks of mutuality and reciprocity – In 2015, the since toppled civilian-led government attempted to modernise and formalise street vending by establishing a completely new market along a major arterial road in Yangon. To maintain their place-based relational connections in the face of displacement, some vendors labelled their stalls according to the street or block they were once located, not only to maintain their previous customer base but also to identify themselves as belonging to that specific place. During the Covid-19 crisis and following the 2021 coup, *nalehmu* practices have continued through street stalls full of food and donations – becoming the only secure lifeline amid state-imposed shortages. Today, Yangon's inhabitants still rely on *nalehmu* networks in their immediate neighbourhoods to survive under military induced precarity. These relations are embedded in a postcolonial setting of actors, spaces, and goods (see also Cobbinah, 2025), which shape urban life through en-

Informality as de-centering practices

Since independence from British colonial rule in 1948, Myanmar has experienced on-going political upheaval and state violence. The brief transition to partial civilian rule between 2011 and 2021 saw manifold development initiatives aimed at modernising and formalising Yangon, almost always according to Global North models of good governance. Funded by international donors, for-

nosing complex power dynamics between various actors that defy universalised theorisation.

Latour's ruminations on scientific critique (2004), however, encourage us to examine the apparent inadequacies of informality as *matters of fact* that need to be transformed into *matters of concern*. Analyses of informality are easily dismissed as regional anecdotes of urban poverty or weapons of the weak (Scott, 1985), when they might, in fact, disguise long-standing, complex and non-hegemonic spatial heuristics hiding in plain sight. In our case, this concerns the postcolonial and complex urban logic of Yangon, Myanmar.

Figurations of Informality: From Burmese *nalehmu* to Chinese *guanxi* to Korean *jeong*

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In some ways, informality as a concept could seem like a debate about semantics. What does informality really mean? How can we better understand its complex relationship to formality beyond a dichotomy? What can it tell us about matters of postcolonial, non-hegemonic, and place-specific modes of operation that constitute space and sustain socio-spatial practices?

To research societal logics across scales and beyond the vagueness of the informality term, it is helpful to approach other relational concepts of spatial logic that are illegible to universalism and are therefore often overlooked as ephemeral, purely personal or other denotations far removed from political relevance.

Burmese *nalehmu*, Chinese *guanxi* and Korean *jeong* all describe concepts of place-specific social mechanisms that share common traits of deepening interpersonal relationships based on trust, reciprocity and prioritising common gain. In their respective contexts, they underpin large parts of everyday life, from the scale of the urban economy down to private life, which contest, superimpose, complement and even shape formalised procedures. What can these concepts tell us, in turn, about our streamlined understandings of space and its legitimate epistemologies and heuristics?

What embodied practices can we find in our immediate surroundings that have evaded our epistemological investigation?

နားလည်မှု

The Burmese concept of *nalehmu* (နားလည်မှု) derives from the notion of understanding (*naleh*) and denotes mutuality and reciprocity between individuals that facilitate social interactions which can promote communal cohesion. It involves recognising and accommodating each other's needs and circumstances based on mutual respect and concern, predicated on the establishment of long-term relationships. Practices of *nalehmu* enable access to goods, services and information, and is negotiated fluidly across intimate and public spheres (Roberts and Rhoads, 2022).

關係

The Chinese concept of *guanxi* (關係) explains a system of strategic relationship-building based on implicit social values such as trustworthiness, mutuality, and proper conduct. While often associated with corruption in state-entanglements, *guanxi* fundamentally underpins long-term relationships, structuring societal interactions through obligation and reciprocity (Yang, 2002).

정

Similarly, in Korean society, the concept of *jeong* (정) describes a culture-specific relational affect that fosters deep, long-term social bonds and feelings of interconnectedness. It is rooted in a Buddhist emphasis on compassion and interconnectedness and Confucian notions of filial piety. *jeong* develops over time through shared experiences and mutual care and encompasses feelings of attachment, empathy, and loyalty among individuals (Chung and Oh, 2025).

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